

Participation of Community through Parents Teacher Councils regarding Curricular and Co-curricular Activities in Public Sector Schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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Abstract

The study focuses on the participation of community through PTC in the arrangement of different curricular and co-curricular activities in schools for betterment of students and enhancement of their qualities. A valid and reliable questionnaire was served to the two categories of stakeholders i.e. PTC members (Chairman and secretary) and Non-PTC members (Parents and Teachers). A sample of one hundred schools randomly selected from two districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Mean, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of variation, t-distribution and p-value were applied as statistical tools. Responses of both groups show moderate response and show that participation of community is found for the first variable i.e. arranging curricular activities but there is opposite opinion found in the point of view of both group regarding the arrangement of co-curricular activities in schools; response of PTC members group is positive but non PTC members group did not support it.

Key Words:

Parent Teacher Council, Community Participation, Curricular Activities, co-Curricular Activities, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa,

Introduction

Community participation in the public sector means involvement of the people in the public schools for the betterment of the institutions. In the school setup, the participation of Community is considered as much necessary as all other educational elements are. For this purpose, different countries have introduced different systems. Some countries have a unique system in order to involve

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community in different matters of the schools, for example, establishment of PTCs etc. in the schools. It was the government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, who first introduced the concept of involvement of community in the schools of especially in public sector. KPK government had a clear vision about the involvement of students' parents in educational matters for the betterment of institute and students. For this purpose, the Elementary Education Foundation (EEF) was established under an ordinance in 2002 for developing a sense of community participation among the people. (Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 2012, p.1).

It was a bold step taken by the government of KPK in order to uplift the deteriorating academic condition of the public institutions. Furthermore, the chairman of the EEF Board of directors was the Chief Minister of KPK, which proved to be very much helpful in decision making. The basic aim of the establishment of EEF was to promote elementary education in the region with the help of community participation. It could be done by sensitizing the people about the issue. The main objectives of EEF were:

- (i) Improving the education at elementary level by involving the members of community,
- (ii) Improving the quality of education by providing training to the teachers,
- (iii) Improving the ratio of participation of community in the educational institutions.
- (iv) Developing a suitable line of action for the madrasa and MAKTAB schools. (Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Elementary Education Foundation, 2012).

The Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is very much enthusiastic and interested to uplift the condition of its institutions, that's why it left no stone unturned for their development. One of the most important steps toward this process was to legalize the involvement of the community in the schools of KPK. The Government extended its legislative support in the year 2005, 2006, 2007 and 2008. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Provincial Reform Program II was publicized by the Government and the title of "Encouraging Public-Private Partnerships and Community Involvement" was given to it. Its clause Number thirty says "the Government of KPK has widened PTAs and enhanced their strength in all twenty thousand primary schools. Accordingly, funds are being provided for construction and minor repairs in order to be utilized by the PTA. Moreover, PTA will likely become more important in the future as they will be assigned some other important activities like observing and reporting teachers' attendance". (Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 2005).

In fact, the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Government worked very hard in order to engage the community in government institutions. For this purpose, the Government began a program in 1999 and it was named as the Education Sector Reform Unit (ESRU). It is quite clear that PTAs were basically introduced at all school levels through this program. The main objective of the introducing Parents Teachers Councils (PTA) was the overall development of educational institutes.

With time, the name of PTA was changed to PTC i.e. Parents Teacher Council was in 2010. After it, the Government of KPK published PTC Guide and enlisted all the responsibilities of Secretary, Chairman and other members. This guide also provides basic information about the composition and formation of PTC. The powers and authorities of PTC are also elucidated in this guide. It is clearly mentioned in the preface of the guide that “PTCs are established to improve the learning environment and physical condition of the school”. Moreover, it is also elucidated in the introduction of PTC guide that the school, students’ parents and the council all of them are directly responsible for improving the school condition. Similarly, the PTC guide also tells us that it is the responsibility of PTCs to get repair and maintenance work done” The PTC guide further explains the powers devolved to the schools i.e. financial and administrative and the PTC is authorized to utilize the funds of school properly. (Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 2011).

Mavis and Steven (2009) explain that the overall development of any educational institution depends on the co-ordination of community members and that institution. Due to this strong coordination, the target of strong academic achievement can be achieved. Children can get quality education from these institutions with the continuous support of community. (P: 25)

Goldring (2008) states parent teacher meetings are the key source for enhancing trust of community on the institutions working in public sector. As in the meeting, the parents discussed different aspects regarding the study of their children and focused discussion was done so school got clear cut direction and way to achieve their way targeted goals set by Government. (P: 2)

Bryan, (2005) describe in his study that school is responsible for the physical, cognitive, social, psychological and economic development of the children and this overall development are possible if institutions initiate different healthy activities like literary and co-curricular activities by involving community especially parents of children.

Different research studies indicate that joint efforts of school and parents are very much necessary for progress of students’ achievement. Failure in the academic is directly linked with the behavior of community, behavior of parents and teachers. If parents take interest in arranging different activities related to their curricula and extracurricular activates the overall development of the child becomes possible (Fan, 2001; Hong & Ho, 2005, Driessen, Smit & Slegers, 2005).

Annunziata *et al* (2006) stated that Failure in academic activities of the children also directly linked with negative attitude of parents, abusing behavior of community, negligence of society, emotional behavior of parents and behavioral problems of society. The students are affected too much from the home and this may badly affect the efficiency of the educational institution. So this hurdle can be removed by creating a close liaison between the parents and school.

Govinda and Diwan (2005) the involvement of community in the curricular and co-curricular activities help in improving quality education, eradicates the different hurdles faced by student and teachers. Community participation support the educational institutions to give nimble the society from ignorance and unawareness. If parents and community supports the public sector schools by providing different facilities, solving immediate issues and provide courage to the principals and teachers about deciding for the betterment and progress of educational institutes.

The main purpose of formation of parents' teacher councils at every school level was to make realize parents about the education of their children, lessen the level of dropout and improve the academic conditions of the children to make them useful person of the society. To develop strong liaison between school and home. Parents and teachers must coordinate and cooperate intelligently for the welfare of general public and special attention on the physical, social, mental and spiritual condition of children. (Government, of Pakistan, 2002).

Kumar (2000) explains that community participation is crucial for the success of all curricular and co-curricular programs, different developmental projects as it enhances sense of ownership and sustainability in the process of development.

Epstein (2006) stated that different researches show that participation of communities and especially families of children play a significant and encouraging role in the field of education in improving learning environment, enhancing learning potential and casting a long-term impact on the behavior of children.

Richard (2011) recommended to distribute time in each day for doing different activities like doing homework, enhance reading habits of children, improving communication skills, time for watching TV, discuss different issues, attending different workshops, activities of selection of career, storytelling and molding behavior of the students.

Smith (2011) explains during the study of parent-teacher association and describes that it is very common thing at the school level and aims to make possible the involvement of parent and society in the progress of educational institutions. When the parents own the educational institute, they try their best for the progress and position of that institute in the society for providing quality education. (P: 12).

Skiba and Strassel (2010) deliberate the role of involvement of parent and community with reference to organize different curricular and co-curricular activities for establishment of a positive atmosphere in educational institutions. They acknowledged six means of involvement of parents; out of these six, three are related to home while other are related to educational institutes. The first three are learning activities at home, parenting and improving communication skills while other three which related to the school are decision making, volunteering and special coordination and collaboration with the community members.

Combs (2008) clearly describes different methods for improving school and community relation. He recommends that:

- (a) All community members are advised to utilize latest means of knowledge.
- (b) Friendly policies for the involvement of community in educational institutions
- (c) Involve talented students in different other activities like games etc
- (d) Granted discount in the purchase of stationary items for those who perform well in curricular and co-curricular activities.
- (e) Special package offers to the intelligent students.
- (f) Certificates must be distributed in the assembly for encouraging for the best performers.
- (g) Family members of different students may be invited for the encouragement and motivation purpose.

Problem Statement

Under the umbrella of existing research, the problem was, “participation of community through parents-teacher councils regarding curricular and co-curricular activities in public sector schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa”.

Research Objectives

Following were the research objectives:

1. To find the participation of community in arranging curricular/co-curricular activities according to views of PTC/Non-PTC members.
2. To find out significant relationship of community through Parent Teacher Council in arranging curricular/co-curricular activities according to views of PTC/non-PTC members.

Research Questions

The research is based on the following research questions:

1. Is there any community participation in arranging curricular activities according to views of PTC members?
2. Is there any participation of community in arranging curricular activities according to views of Non-PTC members?
3. Is there any participation of community in arranging Co-Curricular activities according to views of PTC members?
4. Is there any participation of community in arranging co-curricular activities according to views of Non-PTC members?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no participation of community through Parent Teacher Council in arranging curricular activities in public schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.
- H₀₂: There is no participation of community through Parent Teacher Council in arranging Co-curricular activities in public schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.
- H₁₁: There is participation of community through Parent Teacher Council in arranging curricular activities in public schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.
- H₁₂: There is participation of community through Parent Teacher Council in arranging curricular activities in public schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Rationale of Research Study

It is as clear as day light that when the community gets involved in different activities performed by school like curricular and co-curricular, school makes progress by leaps and bounds and it very soon touches the heights of success as the community can help a lot in arranging different activities inside i.e. curricular and outside the school i.e. co-curricular. The present study is significant in this regard as it depicts, figures out and evaluates the involvement rate of the community in all these activities. This study can be helpful in reframing the PTCs and their responsibilities. Moreover, this study can also motivate the community to take part in all such activities with great enthusiasm which will automatically uplift the academic condition of the school.

Research Methodology

Design of the Study

The researcher wanted to explore the analysis of different views of stakeholders about curricular and co-curricular in the school. The population from which researcher want to explore is known as descriptive research. The design of study was descriptive in nature and self-made questionnaire was used to get responses from different stakeholders after finding its validity and reliability. (Creswell, 2011)

Population and Sample of the Study

There are 1298 male government primary schools in District Dera Ismail Khan and Peshawar. All these schools i.e. 1298 schools are the total study's population while the study's sample was selected by applying sample selection method propounded by Krejcie and Morgan. The total number of selected schools included in the

sample was 580, out of which 230 schools were from Peshawar District and 250 schools were from district Dera Ismail Khan. PTC committees had already been established in all these schools according to the educational policy of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The stakeholders of the study are 04 for each school, out of which two stakeholders are the members of PTC committee while the other two stakeholders are not members of PTC but they are from school and community. Secretary, the head of school and Chairman, the parent of a student are PTC members. The other two non PTC stakeholders are a teacher of that school and parents of those children who are enrolled in these schools. Thus, two very popular sampling techniques were applied to get the sample. First, cluster random sampling technique and then simple random sampling technique were applied.

Table 1. Population of Study

S.No	Name of Districts	Number of GPS/PTC Committees	Community Members who are in PTC Committee		Community Members who are not in PTC Committee	
			No. of Chairmen	No. of G/Secretaries	No. of Teachers	No. of Parents
1	D.I.Khan	715	715	765	715	715
2	Peshawar	583	583	598	583	583
	Total	1298	1298	1298	1298	1298

Table 2. Sample of Study

S.No	Name of Districts	Number of GPS/PTC Committees	Community Members who are in PTC Committee		Community Members who are not in PTC Committee	
			No. of Chairmen	No. of G/Secretaries	No. of Teachers	No. of Parents
1	D.I.Khan	250	250	250	250	250
2	Peshawar	230	230	230	230	230
	Total	480	480	480	480	480

Research Tools

The responses were gathered from the stakeholders through a close ended questionnaire which had a total of eighteen questions. Ten out of eighteen questions were about curricular activities while eight questions were about co-curricular activities.

Validity/Reliability of Research Tool

The research tool used to get responses was developed on a five-point Likert scale with the help of related material and literature. After that, it was presented before the educationists and educational experts to confirm its content validity. Pilot testing was also performed on a small sample of 10 stake holders from each category. After that, for finding reliability Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used. By using Cornbrash's Alpha in SPSS, the value researchers got from it was 0.87. After that in order to find out the item inter-item correlation, Pearson correlation was applied and got the significance level of 0.01.

Procedure of the Research Study

This study was descriptive and it interpreted different viewpoints and facts of stakeholders. The researcher developed a questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale to get responses from the stakeholders. The tool was validated through experts/educationist and its reliability was detected by applying statistical tool Cronbach Alpha which was read as 0.87. The reliable and validated tool consists of 10 items about curricular activities and 08 items about co-curricular activities that were served to the stakeholders.

Data Collection and Interpretation

After collecting the data, it was analyzed with the help of computer software used for Social Sciences i.e. SPSS. Standard Deviation, Mean, t-distribution and coefficient of variance were used to get the results in order to draw inferences and to interpret them.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table 3. Shows Participation of Community about Arranging Curricular Activities as per views of Community Members who are also Members of Pct. Committee

s.no	arranging curricular activities	PTC members	Mean	S. D	C.V	t-Calculated	t-tabulated	P-value
1	Help staff	Chairman	3.86	0.75	19.43	2.01	±1.99	0.004
		Secretary	3.12	0.47	15.06			
2	Provision of temporary Teachers	Chairman	2.32	0.62	26.72	1.22	±1.99	0.067
		Secretary	2.21	0.51	23.07			
3	Conducting Monthly Test	Chairman	3.67	0.67	18.25	3.01	±1.99	0.008
		Secretary	4.51	0.65	14.41			

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4	Conducting Annual Examination	Chairman	3.32	0.76	22.89	-2.45	±1.99	0.001
		Secretary	3.78	0.47	12.43			
5	Generating individual progress reports	Chairman	3.65	0.41	11.25	2.43	±1.99	0.02
		Secretary	3.70	0.67	18.10			
6	Discuss progress of students with Parents	Chairman	3.79	0.46	12.13	-2.33	±1.99	0.005
		Secretary	3.99	0.43	10.77			
7	Arranging PTM	Chairman	4.44	0.65	14.63	2.62	±1.99	0.000
		Secretary	4.35	0.48	11.03			
8	Discuss different problems with parents in PTM	Chairman	3.95	0.54	13.67	2.77	±1.99	0.000
		Secretary	4.09	0.59	14.42			
9	Diagnosing different educational issues of teachers and students.	Chairman	3.91	0.65	16.62	3.01	±1.99	0.005
		Secretary	4.71	0.58	12.31			
10	Addressing different problem faced by teacher and students.	Chairman	3.45	0.43	12.46	3.08	±1.99	0.004
		Secretary	3.99	0.41	10.27			

The above table describes the responses of stakeholders who are members of PTC committee as well as also the active members of community i.e. chairman and secretaries who were considered as most important. The range of mean value is 1-5 but the mean value of item No. 02 (Provision of temporary teacher when needed) is below the average mean value while the calculated t-value is 1.22 which falls in acceptance region so this result lead toward the acceptance of null hypothesis and rejection of alternate hypothesis H_1 which says that there is no significant participation of community through PTC in arranging curricular activities especially in provision of temporary teacher while mean values of other nine items are greater than 2.5 which clearly indicates that there is greater participation of community through PTCs in arranging curricular activities. Similarly, the value of coefficient of variation ranges from 10.27 to 26.72 which shows less dispersion rate. Calculated values of all items except one, which discussed earlier fall in the rejection region, so accept alternative hypothesis H_1 which shows that there is significant participation of community through PTCs in arranging curricular

activities in schools. P-value of responses of both the stakeholders in nine items falls between 0.000 to 0.009 which is less than 0.05 and reflects greater participation rate of community through PTC in arranging curricular activities in public sector schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 4. Shows Participation of Community about Arranging Curricular Activities as per views of Community members who are not members of PTC Committee

S	Arranging curricular activities	PTC members	Mean	S. D	C.V	t-Calculated	t-tabulated	P-value
1	Help staff	Teacher	2.90	0.35	12.06	2.89	±1.99	0.001
		Parent	2.96	0.67	22.63			
2	Provision of temporary Teachers	Teacher	1.76	0.46	26.13	1.78	±1.99	0.004
		Parent	1.87	0.86	45.98			
3	Conducting Monthly Test	Teacher	3.44	0.45	13.08	2.67	±1.99	0.005
		Parent	3.77	0.87	23.07			
4	Conducting Annual Examination	Teacher	3.98	0.83	20.85	-2.57	±1.99	0.007
		Parent	3.66	0.91	24.86			
5	Generating individual progress reports	Teacher	2.45	0.41	16.73	2.58	±1.99	0.009
		Parent	2.32	0.52	22.41			
6	Discuss progress of students with Parents	Teacher	2.13	0.46	12.13	1.70	±1.99	0.004
		Parent	2.11	0.41	19.43			
7	Arranging PTM	Teacher	3.67	0.64	17.82	-2.51	±1.99	0.000
		Parent	3.89	0.49	12.59			
8	Discuss different problems with parents in PTM	Teacher	2.41	0.64	26.55	2.78	±1.99	0.001
		Parent	2.21	0.59	26.69			
9	Diagnosing different educational issues of teachers and students.	Teacher	2.71	0.65	23.98	2.47	±1.99	0.001
		Parent	2.23	0.58	26.00			
10	Addressing different problems faced by teachers and students	Teacher	2.36	0.43	18.22	1.87	±1.99	0.004
		Parent	2.14	0.51	23.83			

The above table shows the perception of two stakeholders who are not members of PTC committees but part of community i.e. teachers and parents. The range of mean value is 1-5 but the mean values of item No. 02(Provision of temporary

teacher when needed), item No.06(Discussing progress with parents) and item No.10 (addressing a different problem faced by teacher and students) are below average mean value and their t-calculated for all three items are 1.78, 1.70 and 1.87 respectively. All the value falls in acceptance region so it leads the acceptance of null hypothesis H₀ and rejection of H₁ which says that there is no significant participation of community through PTCs in arranging curricular activities but all other seven items have mean value greater than 2.5 against the range of 1-5 which clearly indicates greater participation of the community through PTC in arranging curricular activities. Similarly, the value of coefficient of variation ranges from 12.13 to 26.69 which shows less dispersion. Moreover, all ten items except three discussed above have calculated values fall in rejection region and so accept H₁ and concluded that there is significant participation of community in arranging curricular activities in schools. Since P-value of the responses of both the respondents in seven items vary between 0.000 and 0.009 which is less than 0.05 and reflects that there is significant participation of community through PTC committees in arranging curricular activities in schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 5. Comparison of Views of Stakeholders about Participation of Community Through PTC in Arranging Curricular Activities

Organization	Stake holders	Arranging Curricular Activities by PTC committee			Comparison					
					Stake Holders			Organization		
		N	Mean	S. D	t-calculated	t- tabulated	P-value	t-calculated	t- tabulated	P-value
PTC Members	Chairman	100	3.12	0.451	2.71	±1.99	0.001	2.67	±1.99	0.006
	Secretary	100	3.71	0.643						
Non-PTC Members	Teachers	100	2.76	0.567	2.45	±1.99	0.003	2.67	±1.99	0.006
	Parents	100	2.84	0.761						

The above table reflects the comparative figures about the perception of both groups of stakeholders i.e. two hundred PTC members in which one hundred are chairmen and one hundred are secretaries/head of institute while second group has two hundred non PTC members including one hundred teachers and one hundred parents whose children are enrolled in the school but they are not a member of this body. The average mean value of responses from respondent No.1 (chairmen) from first group is 3.12 while the average mean value of respondent No.2 (secretaries) from first group is 3.17. Similarly, the average mean value of respondent No.1 in second group (Teacher) is 2.76 and the average mean value of respondent No.2 (Parent) of second group is 2.84. The range of mean value is 1-5

thus it is apparently seen that the value of average response is greater than 2.5 which shows participation rate of community in arranging curricular activities in the educational institutions i.e. schools in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Likewise, the average value of standard deviation of first respondent (Chairmen) from first group i.e. PTC members is 0.451 while for second respondent (secretaries) of the first group is 0.643. Similarly the average value of standard deviation of second respondent (teacher) from second group i.e. Non-PTC members is 0.567 while for second respondent (parent) of the second group is 0.761. In the same way, the analysis of P-value observed in both groups highlighted the P- value for first group i.e. PTC members is 0.001 and for second group it is 0.003. On the other hand, the P-value is 0.001 and 0.003 respectively for 1st and 2nd group which reflects that the P-value for both the groups is less than 0.05. Similarly, t-calculated value is 2.71 for first group and 2.45 for the second group. Both the values fall in the rejection region of t-tabulated i.e. ± 1.99 which indicates rejection of H_0 and acceptance of H_1 which indicates that there is significant participation of community through PTC in arranging curricular activities in the schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The average P-value for both the groups is 0.006 which is again less than 0.05 and the average t-calculated value for both the groups is 2.67 which is greater than the t-tabulated i.e. ± 1.99 . Thus, H_0 is easily rejected and H_1 is accepted which says that there is significant participation of community through PTC arranging curricular activities in schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 6. Shows Participation of Community about Arranging Co-Curricular Activities as per views of Community members who are also members of PTC Committee

S	arranging Co-Curricular activities	PTC members	Mean	S. D	C.V	t- Calculated	t- tabulated	P- value
1	Arrange Literary Competitions	Chairman	3.86	0.27	6.99	2.89	± 1.99	0.001
		Secretary	3.67	0.45	12.26			
2	Organizing different programs at National Festivals	Chairman	2.81	0.95	23.80	1.68	± 1.99	0.604
		Secretary	3.65	0.99	27.12			
3	Organize programs for character Building	Chairman	2.57	0.77	19.96	0.98	± 1.99	0.405
		Secretary	3.23	0.67	20.74			
4	Ensure right to play for students	Chairman	2.32	0.83	25.77	-2.07	± 1.99	0.507
		Secretary	3.12	0.61	19.55			
5	Plan sports competitions	Chairman	2.34	0.41	17.52	2.58	± 1.99	0.079
		Secretary	2.75	0.32	11.63			
6	organize Sports Competitions	Chairman	2.88	0.46	15.97	2.70	± 1.99	0.004
		Secretary	3.69	0.41	11.11			
7	Ensure participation of community member	Chairman	2.59	0.64	24.71	-2.62	± 1.99	0.000
		Secretary	3.85	0.49	12.72			
8		Chairman	3.85	0.64	16.62	2.87	± 1.99	0.001

	Ensure participation of Elected member	Secretary	3.99	0.59	14.78			
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This table shows the responses of stakeholders who are members of PTC committee as well as the active members of community i.e. chairman and secretary. The range of mean value is 1-5 but the mean value of item No.4 and item No.5 (Ensure right to play for students and plan sports competitions) are below average mean value and their t-calculated values are -2.07 and 2.58 respectively, Both fall in acceptance region which leads the acceptance of null hypothesis that there is no such participation rate of community through PTCs committee especially in these two aspects. All other six items have their mean value greater than 2.5 i.e. average mean value which indicates the community participation thorough PTCs committee in arranging co-curricular activities. The analysis of values of coefficient of variation which ranges from 06.99 to 27.12, shows less dispersion rate. Calculated values of t of all items except two discussed above falls in rejection region which shows the participation rate of community is better as per perception of stakeholders i.e. chairmen and secretaries of PTC committees. Since the p-values of the respondents in the six items in between 0.001 to 0.009 is lesser than 0.05, it reflects a significant participation of community through PTC committees in arranging co-curricular activities in schools functioning under the government sector in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 7. Shows Participation of community about Arranging Co-Curricular Activities as per views of community members who are not members of PTC Committee

S	arranging Co-Curricular activities	PTC members	Mean	S. D	C.V	t-Calculated	t-tabulated	P-value
1	Arrange Literary Competitions	Teacher	2.46	0.67	27.23	1.89	±1.99	0.071
		Parent	2.12	1.01	47.64			
2	Organizing different programs at National Festivals	Teacher	2.45	0.56	18.98	1.78	±1.99	0.204
		Parent	2.34	0.46	19.65			
3	Organize programs for character Building	Teacher	2.27	0.77	33.92	-1.67	±1.99	0.145
		Parent	2.23	0.64	28.69			
4	Ensure right to play for students	Teacher	2.32	0.34	10.24	-1.60	±1.99	0.107
		Parent	2.12	0.87	41.03			
5	Plan sports competitions	Teacher	2.78	0.43	15.46	2.58	±1.99	0.009
		Parent	2.70	0.52	19.25			
6	organize Sports Competitions	Teacher	3.41	0.46	13.48	2.70	±1.99	0.004
		Parent	2.69	0.41	15.24			
7	Ensure participation of community member	Teacher	2.59	0.64	24.71	-2.62	±1.99	0.008
		Parent	2.85	0.49	17.19			

8	Ensure participation of Elected member	Teacher	3.21	0.64	19.93	2.87	±1.99	0.001
		Parent	2.89	0.59	20.41			

The above table shows perception of two stakeholders who are not members of PTC committees but part of community i.e. teachers and parents. The range of mean value is 1-5 but the mean values of item No. 01 to item No.04 which are arrange literary competitions, organize different program at National festivals, for the purpose of character building of students. The organized programs were below average mean value and their t-calculated values are 1.89, 1.78, -1.60 and 1.87 respectively. All the value fall in acceptance region so it leads the acceptance of null hypothesis H₀ and rejection of H₁ which says that there is no significant participation of community through PTCs in arranging co-curricular activities. But all other four items have mean value greater than 2.5 against the range of 1-5 which clearly indicates greater participation of the community through PTC in arranging curricular activities. Similarly, the value of coefficient of variation ranges from 10.24 to 47.64 showing less dispersion. Moreover, all other four items except four discussed above have calculated values falling in rejection region and so accepted H₁ and concluded that there is significant participation of community regarding arrangement of co-curricular activities in public sector schools. As the P-value of the responses of both the respondents in first four items varies from 0.071 to 0.107, while last four items ranges from 0.001 to and 0.009 which is less than 0.05 and reflects a significant participation of community through PTC committees in arranging co-curricular activities in schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 8. Comparison of views of Stakeholders about Participation of Community Through PTC in Arranging Co-Curricular Activities

Organization	Stake holders	Arranging Co-Curricular Activities by PTC committee			Comparison					
					Stakeholders			Organization		
		N	Mean	S. D	t-calculated	t-tabulated	P-value	t-calculated	t-tabulated	P-value
PTC Members	Chairman	100	2.71	0.532	1.76	±1.99	0.301	1.66	±1.99	0.205
	Secretary	100	3.46	0.432						
Non-PTC Members	Teachers	100	2.91	0.321	1.63	±1.99	0.413	1.66	±1.99	0.205
	Parents	100	2.71	0.445						

The above table reflect the comparative figures about the perception of both groups of stakeholders i.e. two hundred non PTC members in which one hundred chairmen and one hundred secretaries/head of institution while second group consist of two hundred non PTC members in which one hundred teachers and one hundred those parents are included whose children are studying in the school but

they are not member of this body. The average mean value of responses from respondent No.1 (chairmen) from first group is 2.71 while the average mean value of respondent No.2 (secretaries) from first group is 3.46 similarly the average mean value of respondent No.1 in second group (Teacher) is 2.91 and the average mean value of respondent No.2 (Parent) of second group is 2.71. Range of mean value is 1-5 thus it is apparently seen that the value of average response is greater than 2.5 which shows participation rate of community in arranging co-curricular activities in educational institutions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. But in the same manner the average value of standard deviation of first respondent (Chairmen) from first group i.e. PTC members is 0.532 while for second respondent (secretaries) of the first group is 0.432. Similarly the average value of standard deviation of second respondent (teacher) from second group i.e. non PTC members is 0.321 while for second respondent (parent) of the second group is 0.445. In the same way when analysis of P- value observed in both groups the P-value for first group i.e. PTC members is 0.301 and for second group it is 0.413 which shows the On the other hand P- values were 0.001 and 0.003 for first and second group respectively which reflect lesser than 0.05 similarly t-calculated for the first group is 1.76 and for the second group is 1.63. Both the values falls in the acceptance region of t-tabulated i.e. ± 1.99 which indicates acceptance of H_0 and rejection of H_1 which indicates that there is no/less significant participation of community through PTC in arrangement of co-curricular activities in educational institutions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The average P-value for both the groups is 0.205 which is again greater than 0.05 and the average t-calculated value for both the groups is 1.66 which is greater than the t-tabulated i.e. ± 1.99 . Thus H_0 is easily accepted and H_1 is rejected which says that there is no/less significant participation of community through PTC arranging co-curricular activities in schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Discussion

From the analysis of above table No.1 to 03 the responses about curricular activities done in the public sector schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. As per perception of 1st pair of stakeholders' i.e. Chairmen and Secretaries who is considered as active members of community as well as the members of PTC committee, Community can help the schools in arranging curricular activities like help the staff members of school, conducting monthly test as well as annual examination at school. Generation of progress reports of individual, arranging PTM/discussion meeting with parents to overcome the shortcoming of the students' and school. Community plays its vital role in diagnosing and addressing the different problems faced by school and students (Fan, 2001; Hong & Ho, 2005 Driessen, Smit & Slegers, 2005).

As perception of second pair of respondents i.e. Teachers and Parents who are

not members of PTC committee about performing curricular activities done in schools they are not agree on the item No.2, 5, 8, 9, &10 (Provision of temporary teachers, generating individual progress reports, Discuss of problem of students with parents, Discuss different problems with parents. diagnosing and addressing different educational issues of teachers/students). All the values show adverse participation rate about these items which clearly indicates the insignificant participation and interest of those community members who are not involved in affairs of schools specially in arranging co-curricular activities. (Kentucky, 2011)

After the analysis of both pairs of stake holders, both have on agreement that there is participation of community in arranging curricular activities, but the responses of second group are slightly weak but show positive response.

While from the analysis of second variable i.e. arranging co-curricular activities the responses of both the pair of stake holders are slightly different, the first pair of respondents who are member of PTC committee are respond positively while the second pair who are not member of PTC committee are shown disagreement with the statement that community is participating in public sector school in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa specially in arranging co-curricular activities. It may be due to fact that as they are not involved in any activity of PTC committee or any business of school so they are only observers. They just observe and respond, so un-awareness is the basic reason behind their low response. If they are active participants then may be their responses become changed. (Skiba and Strassel 2010)

As a statistic t-calculated value of both pair of groups shows strong agreement between stake holders and show that there is participation of community in public sector schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in arranging co-curricular activities.

Conclusion

From the discussion of above six tables, it can easily be concluded that that there is great participation of community in curricular activities according to first group i.e. PTC members but there is little bit fluctuation found in the perception and viewpoints of second group. (i.e. Non-PTC Members) which they show less participation in three item out of ten and reject that community has no/less participation in arranging activities related to curricular aspect in the government schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Second variable which was about arrangement of co-curricular activities in the primary schools, according to the perception of first group is towards the acceptance mode of and they are agree with seven items out of ten but view point of second group is quite different from the view point of first their perception is toward the null hypothesis and concluded that there is no strong participation of community in arranging co-curricular activities in the school. From the variation

in the view points of both the groups it can be concluded that due to non-attachment in the affair of PTC committees and their assigned tasks the non PTC members are un-aware for the mandate and functioning of PTC committees. So it is better that awareness sessions may be arrange for all the parents whose children are studying in government school and initiate so many efforts to take interest in the business of school activities for the welfare and better progress of the children in their educational and then professional life.

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